

Controlled assembly of thiorphan molecules into nanostructures on polar and nonpolar ZnO surfaces: correlative AFM-in-SEM analysis

Molecules can form different structures on substrates inspite of the same material composition. Reasons can be different surface polarity or surface chemistry. The AFM-in-SEM correlation reveals that the opposite contrast in SEM reflects different structure of biomolecular assembly on the surface depending on the surface dipole orientation.

AFM-in-SEM data shows clear correlation between secondary electron intensity from thiorphan molecules in SEM and their height in AFM on polar ZnO surfaces whereas anti-correlation is observed on nonpolar ZnO surfaces. The secondary electron emission from the same biomolecule thus depends on its orientation, structure it assembles into, and it can be moreover controlled by the direction of the substrate dipole.

The thiorphan assembly on different ZnO surfaces was studied by CPEM (AFM-in-SEM). The correlative CPEM data from the same region of interest were obtained under the same conditions simultaneously. The data reveal that depending on ZnO surface dipole orientation, thiorphan molecular structures may have either higher (on the polar O-face ZnO surface) or lower (on the nonpolar surface) SE or BSE intensity. The effect has been attributed to enhanced electron emission or backscattering in the first case and to electron shading mechanism in the latter case. Such direct height/BSE correlation on nanoscale features would be hard to obtain by separate AFM and SEM imaging.

The results also hint at possibly a more general effect where the same material (molecular or other) in differently assembled structures (that can be controlled by substrate dipoles or electric field in general) can result in opposite SE and BSE contrast on the same substrate material. Such correlation CPEM technique can be used in many other fields of science.

Figure 4: Setup for measurement of thiorphan molecular structures on ZnO crystal substrates by using AFM-in-SEM method.

